

This text contains information about additional files which are not included in the main manuscript (paper). The movie “Space stem precursor formation dynamics”, some frames of which (in reduced form) are shown in Fig. 7 of the main manuscript (paper) and in Fig. AF4, visualizes a typical example of the model realization which ends with formation of a space stem precursor in the ground-level conditions. Additional figures (AF1-AF12) present several examples of space stem precursors under different simulation conditions. Figs. A4 and A5 correspond to Figs. 7 and 8 of the main manuscript (paper), respectively, and some fragments of several other additional figures are shown in Fig. 9 of the main manuscript (paper). In each figure the upper panel shows a floating quasi anode just before the last (triggering) streamer head stopping, the middle panel corresponds to the moment when the last negative streamer head stops in front of the positively charged region, and the bottom panel presents the latest stage of the system development at which the charge of the last stopped streamer head becomes a source of an electron avalanche. The last can further transform into a positive streamer growing in the opposite direction. The movie and figures give information about the following physical quantities: electron concentration (n_e), concentrations of positive ($n_p = n_{p1} + n_{p2} + n_{p3}$) and negative ($n_n = n_{n1} + n_{n2} + n_{n3}$) ions, the total system charge (q), electric field strength (E), ionization ($\nu_i = \nu_{i1} + \nu_{i2}$), attachment ($\nu_a = \nu_{a1} + \nu_{a2} + \nu_{a3}$), and detachment ($\nu_d = \nu_{d1} + \nu_{d2} + \nu_{d3}$) frequencies, and an increment of the charge carriers growth (λ^+). Detailed information about the model realizations shown in additional figures is presented in the Table below. In this table h is an altitude above sea level, N_h is the number of the negative streamer heads contributed to a quasi anode formation, t_{stop}^i ($i=1:N_h$) are the moments of time corresponding to the stopping of i -th streamer head (it is assumed that $t_{\text{stop}}^1 = 0$ ns), t_{fin} is the moment of time at which the last (triggering) negative streamer head stops, q_p is the total charge of a quasi-anode just before the moment $t = t_{\text{fin}}$, and q_{th} is the threshold (minimal) value of a quasi-anode charge given here for reference.

Table. Details of model realizations shown in Figs. AF1-AF12.

Figure	h , km	N_h	t_{stop}^2 , ns	t_{stop}^3 , ns	t_{stop}^4 , ns	t_{stop}^5 , ns	t_{stop}^6 , ns	t_{stop}^7 , ns	t_{stop}^8 , ns	t_{fin} , ns	q_p , pC	q_{th} , pC
AF1	0	6	2.7	3.5	4.5	5.0	5.9	81.4	-	89.1	18.4	10.0
AF2	0	6	1.5	2.1	2.8	3.2	3.9	57.0	-	58.9	20.1	10.0
AF3	0	7	2.0	3.2	4.5	5.2	5.8	6.5	55.7	62.3	15.2	10.0
AF4	0	6	2.1	2.8	4.5	5.3	6.5	80.9	-	88.5	13.9	10.0
AF5	0	5	1.3	1.6	2.0	2.2	56.8	-	-	58.3	10.7	10.0
AF6	4	5	1.6	2.5	3.1	3.7	86.0	-	-	90.2	18.6	15.2
AF7	4	7	3.3	5.0	7.1	8.3	10.1	11.2	101.3	103.6	21.4	15.2
AF8	4	7	2.9	4.5	6.4	8.4	10.1	11.6	108.1	111.4	22.3	15.2
AF9	8	6	3.6	5.4	6.8	8.1	9.8	157.1	-	161.2	27.1	23.9
AF10	8	7	7.3	11.4	14.3	17.5	20.0	22.3	214.8	217.9	34.9	23.9
AF11	12	7	9.9	16.5	21.9	27.5	32.6	35.8	273.6	282.5	76.7	39.0
AF12	12	7	9.1	18.1	27.1	35.0	38.6	42.0	316.2	327.0	105.2	39.0